

PLASTIC PACKAGING IN PEOPLE'S LIVES

Plastic Packaging in People's Lives Malaysia Pilot:

Household and Waste Management Practices

Plastics play a critical role in society and the economy in Malaysia. Plastic pollution has sparked debate about waste management, environmental and health impacts. The Malaysian Plastic Sustainability Roadmap (MPSR) 2021-2030 aims to coordinate action.

Knowledge from research is essential to support Malaysia's move to a circular zero waste society.

Key challenges

Speaking to ten households and eight organisations, six key challenges were identified.

Plastic packaging overconsumption

Plastics delayed from entering waste streams

Lack of clear guidance about waste practices

Infrastructure for plastic recycling

Capturing quality plastic packaging recyclables

Navigating regulated and unregulated practices

Opportunities

There are four clear opportunities that support the ambitions of the MPSR.

Reduce consumption of single-use plastics

Enhancing consumer education on recycling practices

Improve material quality by reducing contamination

Improve data collection and transparency from recycling collection facilities

Future research

Three research agendas emerged to move towards a circular zero waste society.

Rethink the consumer attitude behaviour gap. Support behavioural shifts to reduce plastic packaging consumption and improve recycling practices.

Map circular material and social flows of plastics. Examine fates for plastic packaging recycling to support high-quality material recapture.

Digital monitoring of material flows. Focus on the role of technology in collecting and recording recycling rates.

Please get in touch to help us expand these research ideas. Let's address the plastic challenges facing this growing economy.

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